

Appendices (Instruments for research: TPACK and Teachers training of mathematics)

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1. APPENDICES

Appendix 1

UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL, COSTA RICA FACULTY OF EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS

Questionnaire on the technological knowledge of mathematics teachers in initial training (MTITs) at the Universidad Nacional.

This instrument has the purpose of collecting data necessary to carry out research on the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge present in mathematics teachers in initial training at the Universidad Nacional, during the I cycle 2020. The information collected will be used only for educational purposes and it will be managed confidentially.

We thank you in advance for your valuable collaboration.

INSTRUCTIONS

Answer the following questions with responsibility and honesty according to the experiences you have had in your training process at this university.

SECTION I

General Information

In this section you will be consulted on general and basic aspects related to your role as a student at the Universidad Nacional.

1. Email address: _____
2. Gender: Female ___ Male ___
3. Age: _____
4. Have you taught classes at the high school level or to particulars: Yes ___ No ___
If your answer is yes, please indicate where: _____
5. Province of origin: _____
6. Current career academic level: _____
7. Have you failed a career course: Yes ___ No ___ (**If you checked NO, go to question 9**)
8. If you have failed a course, indicate the name of the course and the number of times you have enrolled it, respectively:

Name of the course:

- A. _____
 B. _____
 C. _____
 D. _____
 E. _____
 F. _____

Times enrolled:

- A. _____
 B. _____
 C. _____
 D. _____
 E. _____
 F. _____

9. Have you approved the course MAC403 Principles of mathematics II: Yes ___ No ___
10. Have you approved the course DEY402 Pedagogical models and learning theories:
Yes ___ No ___
11. What courses are you currently enrolled in?

SECTION II

Technological knowledge

In this section you will be consulted on aspects related to the teaching of functions and the use of technology.

1. Answer according to your criteria and understanding that MD = Strongly disagree; D = Disagree; N = Neither disagree nor agree; A = Agree; DA = Strongly agree.

	MD	D	N	A	DA
1. I can solve basic technical problems with technology.					

2. I assimilate technological knowledge easily.					
3. I keep up to date with important new technologies.					
4. I often play and test with technology.					
5. I know many different types of technologies.					
6. I possess the technical knowledge required to use technology.					
7. I have had enough opportunities to work with different technologies.					
8. I am comfortable using technology.					

2. At your discretion, discuss some of the errors that often occur in teaching the quadratic function.

3. From the following technological tools, select with **X** those that you consider appropriate for teaching quadratic function.

	Yes	No	Not known
GeoGebra			
Excel			
Winplot			
Virtual forums			
YouTube			
Wolfram Alpha			
RStudio			
Sketchpad			
Mathematica			

4. Discuss how the software you selected could help overcome the difficulties considered in question 2.

5. When you do not know a concept or information about mathematical content, do you search the web? Yes ____ No ____

6. In the space below, you can suggest other technologies that you consider appropriate for teaching functions.

7. Discuss, broadly, the advantages or disadvantages that you consider to be present when using technology in mathematics class.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION

Appendix 2

UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL, COSTA RICA FACULTY OF EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS

Activity on TPACK knowledge of mathematics teachers in initial training at the Universidad Nacional.

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INSTRUCTIONS

Answer in a clear and orderly manner, use the knowledge you have acquired during your training process.

1. Select the aspects that you consider can influence the teaching and learning process
 - a) Classroom condition (lighting, ventilation, appropriate seats, etc.)
 - b) Assertive teacher-student communication
 - c) Assertive student-teacher communication
 - d) Relevant teaching resources (adequate and sufficient)
 - e) Teacher's knowledge on the subject

2. Write down other aspects that you consider important:

Notes for researchers:

This question allows to recognize factors that MTITs consider influence the learning process and this facilitates the characterization of his/her pedagogical knowledge.

3. Explain in your own words which pedagogical model you would employ the most when teaching mathematics and why (lectures, collaborative work, problem solving or others).

Notes for researchers:

This question allows to recognize the position that the participant holds regarding the principal methodologies in teaching, it can evidence his/her pedagogical knowledge by way of the provided justification for selecting a specific methodology.

4. Enunciate one possible definition of a quadratic function.

Notes for researchers:

This question allows to measure whether the student (MTIT) provides an adequate definition of the concept of quadratic function. Furthermore, it is intended for the MTIT to provide a definition, in words or using mathematical language, as taught in the course MAC403 Principles of Mathematics II.

Expected definitions:

- The quadratic function is a second degree polynomial function that is defined for every real number.
- Function $f: D \rightarrow R$ with $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$ where $a, b, c \in R$ y $a \neq 0$.

5. Consider the following situation:

The entrance to a building measures 2.25 meters high at its center, 3 meters wide at the base, and is shaped like a parabolic arch.

Determine the **criterion** of the function that models the building's entrance arch.

6. Graph the function found with GeoGebra software and save the file as **Studentname_animation_1.ggb**.
7. If a rectangular box must be passed through the previously mentioned building entrance, and the box measures 2 meters high, but cannot be turned over (flipped) due to the contents it carries: What is the maximum width (in meters) that the box can have?

Notes for researchers:

This question allows to know if the MTIT can find the quadratic expression that describes the situation (context), and also, if the individual is capable of graphing functions in GeoGebra. Thus, it provides evidence of the MTIT's knowledge of technology and functions.

It is intended for the student (MTIT) to identify the intersections with the X axis and thus be able to find the algebraic expression. Furthermore, since the parabola that intersects the X axis at two points is not unique, the MTIT must analyze the concavity of the equation found and reflect on whether the expression corresponds to the presented situation or not. If the concavity does not coincide, the MTIT is expected to reconsider his/her procedures and be able to formulate the correct equation.

8. Consider the following situation:

A function that models the height position, in meters, of a baseball thrown by a child has as association criterion $f(x) = -\frac{1}{3}x^2 + 3x + 1.83$, where x is the horizontal distance (in meters) from where the ball was thrown.

Determine the domain and range of the function of the presented situation; if desired, graph the function using GeoGebra software.

9. Interpret the domain and range of the above function according to the context (the height of the ball and the distance).
10. Using GeoGebra software, create an animated representation (simulation) of the situation considering the determined domain, that is, create a sliding cursor (point) simulating the trajectory of the baseball. Name the file **Studentname_animation_2.ggb**.
11. Stop the movement of the cursor at any point on the graph curve (created in the previous exercise) and identify the X and Y coordinates at that point. How does the Y coordinate relate to the X coordinate within the context?
12. Find the axis of symmetry of the given function and explain in your own words its meaning within the context.

Notes for researchers:

This question allows to evidence the state of knowledge of MTITs on functions, also, it allows them to exhibit their pedagogical and technological knowledge on the subject, specifically, if they know how to determine the domain of a function according to the context and perform animations using software. It is expected for MTITs to identify that under the provided context, the domain and range cannot be negative, in addition, it is aspired that students be able to correctly manipulate GeoGebra software and use the **if then** function, and insert a sliding cursor (point) simulating the trajectory of the baseball.

13. Discuss how to approach the subject of quadratic function for a tenth (10th) grade

Notes for researchers:

It is expected of MTITs to know the contents that are taught in high school on the subject of quadratic function and be able to propose a suitable sequence for its teaching.

audience.

14. Describe in detail how you would organize a class to teach this subject (10th grade) if you were the teacher. Be as specific as possible.

Notes for researchers:

The MTIT is expected to demonstrate his/her knowledge of teaching the subject of functions and to properly use GeoGebra software and, additionally, to be able to propose pedagogical techniques that facilitate the learning of the subject by employing the aforementioned software.

15. Follow the instructions below

- a. Construct a model situation to introduce the subject of quadratic function at the level of secondary education mathematics using GeoGebra software.
- b. Open a document in Word and write the instructions to execute the activity you constructed. Name the file **StudentName_Instructions.docx**. Name the GeoGebra file **StudentName_situation.ggb**.
- c. Email the following files
 - **StudentName_animación_1.ggb**
 - **StudentName_animation_2.ggb**
 - **StudentName_Instructions.docx**
 - **StudentName_situation.ggb**

To the following addresses: **XX**

- d. In the **Activities and instructions** forum, submit one comment and place as attachments the instructions (Word file) and GeoGebra file.

Notes for researchers:

It is expected for the instructions created by MTITs to be clear and evidence an adequate sequence for the development of the subject, with methodological strategies that promote understanding and favor conceptual and procedural development, as well as the appropriate manner of employing the different semiotic representations.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION

Appendix 3

**UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL, COSTA RICA
FACULTY OF EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES
SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS**

Activity for reflecting on the proposal of the instructions guide created by mathematics teachers in initial training (MTIT) at the Universidad Nacional.

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INSTRUCTIONS

Perform the following tasks with responsibility and honesty, answer what is requested in a clear and orderly manner, use the knowledge you have obtained during your training process.

1. You will be assigned the instructions guide created by another colleague. Carry out the proposal that was assigned to you.

Notes for researchers:

Emerging categories may derive from this item, since MTITs are at liberty to create the instruction guides. It could be the case that as a result of the analysis of these guides, MTITs might exhibit knowledge that has not been foreseen.

2. Evaluate the proposal and instructions created by your colleague, provide justified comments and recommendations to improve both items.

Notes for researchers:

This item seeks to know if MTITs, within their analysis, take into account aspects such as: the semiotic representation that best adapts to the problem situation, use of the appropriate technological resource to facilitate student learning, and the difficulties that may arise for learning the subject.

3. Write a detailed comment in the forum, describing the observations you gathered from the previous evaluation (second item).

Notes for researchers:

This item seeks to know if MTITs reflect on how the teacher's decisions and instructions influence the learning process, it is expected for this reflection to be evidenced in the suggestions and justifications provided by MTITs.

4. Consider the recommendations given to improve your activity and justify why these modifications should be accepted or rejected.

Notes for researchers:

This item seeks to know if MTITs reflect on aspects such as: the semiotic representation that best adapts to the problem situation context, the technological resources that can facilitate students' work and the difficulties that may arise for learning the subject, and the acceptance or rejection of the modifications proposed by colleagues.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION